

TITLE PAGE

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Impact of hospitalization of people with dementia or cognitive impairment on their informal caregivers

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Acknowledgements

We would like to thank all the staff in the traumatology unit involved in this project.

Blinded information

Line 84: Hospital Clinic, Barcelona (Catalonia), Hospital Universitario Marqués de Valdecilla (Cantabria) and Hospital Universitario de Navarra (Navarra).

Line 133: Comité Ético Hospital Clinic, Barcelona (HCB/2017/0499), Comité Ético de Investigación Clínica de Cantabria IDIVAL (2017.241) and Comité de Ética Navarra (Pyto2017/39)

Line 161: (Casafont et al., 2022)

1 Abstract

2
3 People with dementia have a higher risk of hospitalization than people without dementia.
4 Hospitalizations are stressful events for people with dementia and their caregivers, representing
5 a considerable change to their routines. This descriptive longitudinal study aimed to identify the
6 positive and negative reactions, experiences related to health and social integrated care,
7 resource utilization and work status of informal caregivers of patients with dementia or
8 cognitive impairment admitted to hospital with a proximal femur fracture undergoing surgery.
9 Findings indicated that informal caregivers (n=174) are fully committed to providing assistance
10 in activities of daily living and supervision showing only positive attitudes on self-esteem and
11 negative attitudes towards lack of family support, impact of finances, impact on schedule and
12 impact on health. Overall caregiver experiences with integrated health and social care improved
13 after hospitalization but decreased after discharge. One month after hospitalization, IC
14 maintained the same work hours but used fewer healthcare resources. Hospitalization
15 represents a good opportunity to approach informal caregivers and determine their needs in
16 order to provide them with interventions to minimize their burden and improve their wellbeing.
17 Keywords: dementia, informal caregiver, hospitalization, resource utilization, care reaction, hip
18 fracture, experience.

19 Introduction

20 Around 50 million people live with dementia worldwide, leading to deterioration in cognitive,
21 functional and social abilities. This has both an economic impact and consequences for the
22 caregivers and families (WHO, 2017). People with dementia (PwD) progressively end up needing
23 someone to care for them, usually within the family. An Informal Caregiver (IC) is considered as
24 a relative or someone close to the family in charge of assisting the person with the activities of
25 daily living with no economic remuneration (Jorgensen et al., 2008).

26 ICs often experience burden when caring for their relative with dementia, driven by the
27 patient's neuropsychiatric symptoms, which include agitation and mood disturbances (Connors
28 et al., 2020). The number of caregiver tasks is proportional to caregiver burden, especially for
29 those living with PwD, and this is linked to emotional distress (Kang et al., 2018). A systematic
30 review found an association between behavioral and neuropsychiatric symptoms and an
31 increase in caregiver burden with ICs presenting, in particular, irritability, agitation/aggression,
32 sleep disturbances, anxiety, apathy and delusion (Terum et al., 2017). Moreover, Kieboom et al.
33 (2020) found that lower functional status in basic activities of daily living (ADL) of PwD was a risk
34 factor for caregiver burden, as patients needed more caregiver supervision.

35 Social resources for dependent people are available when these cannot be autonomous on their
36 daily activities. However, it takes a long time to get an approval and generally they do not cover
37 all the assistance they need for daily activities and support for informal caregivers. Additionally,
38 cultural traditions tend to assume caregiving as an obligation and responsibility, hence they do
39 not look for help from professionals in the early stages (Moreno-Cámara et al., 2019)(Del-Pino-
40 Casado et al., 2011), which increases their chances of burnout. Caregiver's reactions to process
41 of care are mostly negative, implying worse wellbeing and quality of life. A study conducted in
42 China, caregivers that experienced negative emotions showed a higher level of caregiver burden
43 (Lan et al., 2021). However, positive reactions have been described in the provision of care to
44 PwD such as personal accomplishment and gratification, family cohesion and functionality, and
45 a sense of personal growth and purpose in life (Yu et al., 2018). In fact, The Caregiver Reaction
46 assessment (CRA) measures not only negative but also positive reactions of caregivers looking
47 after PwD. This enables healthcare professionals to take action avoiding physical and emotional
48 overload in caregivers (Alvira et al., 2020).

49 People with dementia have a higher risk (1.42 times higher) of hospitalization than people
50 without dementia (Shepherd et al., 2019). Hospitalizations are stressful events for PwD and their

51 family members which often leave ICs feeling physically and emotionally exhausted. This distress
52 is due to the reason for admission and concern about the patient's mental state and general
53 deterioration throughout the hospitalization process (Beardon et al., 2018). PwD are admitted
54 to specialized wards according to their medical reason for admission, not dementia wards. ICs
55 often feel these are unsuitable to deal with their distress and confusion and lead to worsening
56 of their mental state and behaviour, nosocomial infections, pressure ulcers and falls (Beardon
57 et al., 2018). Furthermore, the patient caregiver dyad should also be considered as someone to
58 care for during hospitalization. Caregiver experiences can be measured in relation to integrated
59 care, where emotional, informational and personal needs also have to be addressed. These
60 experiences are based on the response to the social and health systems, and the identification
61 of gaps at an organizational level (Guilabert et al., 2018). In addition, returning home after
62 hospitalization can be challenging for caregivers. Those who are employed may have difficulties
63 balancing work and caregiving activities. A study in Canada reported that caregivers dealing with
64 dementia that placed high demands on them worked the same hours and had the same job type
65 as those managing dementia with lower demands or caregivers of people without dementia,
66 suggesting that they are keen to maintain work productivity and avoid reducing work hours,
67 even when dealing with increased stress, depressed mood and burden (Sadavoy et al., 2022).
68 However, employed ICs of PwD with more working hours who are less efficient at work are more
69 likely to have a poorer quality of life (Wang et al., 2020). In fact, ICs have a higher risk of losing
70 their jobs or having fewer promotion prospects in their careers (Peña-Longobardo et al., 2021).
71 This also reflects the lack of time that informal caregivers have for their self-care, being
72 emotional or physical care. It is fundamental to identify their use of social and healthcare
73 resources after their relative's discharge. Development of new strategies should be considered
74 to support ICs.

75 Due to the fact that there is not much evidence on IC of PwD requiring hospitalization, the aim
76 of this study is to analyse the profile of ICs of people with dementia or cognitive impairment
77 hospitalized with a proximal femur fracture requiring surgery:

- 78 - To identify positive and negative reactions of informal caregivers in relation to caring
- 79 - To describe the experience of informal caregivers in relation to the health and social
80 integrated care that receive the persons they care for.
- 81 - To analyse the resource utilization and work status of informal caregivers

82 This knowledge is essential for the development of interventions to improve IC quality of life.

83 **Methods**

84 **Design**

85 This study belongs to a larger project called Care of older people with Cognitive Impairment or
86 Dementia Hospitalized in Traumatology Units (CARExDEM). A multicentric descriptive
87 longitudinal study was conducted. Further details are published elsewhere (BLINDED et al.,
88 2022).

89 **Setting**

90 The study was conducted in three traumatology units at high technology public hospitals across
91 Spain: BLINDED.

92 **Participants**

93 Participants were ICs of PwD or patients with cognitive impairment (n=174) hospitalized with
94 proximal femur fracture requiring surgery. Inclusion criteria for PwD were: (a) patients older
95 than 65 hospitalized for surgery, (b) a score of 5 or higher in the Short Portable Mental Status
96 Questionnaire (SPMSQ) test indicating moderate to severe cognitive impairment, and (c) having

97 a signed informed consent form. Exclusion criteria for PwD were: (a) patients younger than 65,
98 (b) psychiatric symptoms or Korsakoff's syndrome, and (c) no informed consent form.

99 Inclusion criteria for informal caregivers were: (a) the person in charge of looking after the
100 patient with dementia, living with him/her or visiting at least three times per week at home or
101 at a nursing home, and (b) having a signed informed consent form.

102 **Data collection**

103 Baseline data collection took place between August 2018 and December 2019 within 24 hours
104 of ward admission and follow-ups were at discharge, and one and three months post-discharge.
105 Data were collected in person by trained nurses with extensive experience in geriatric
106 orthopaedics. Data collected at three months post-discharge was conducted by telephone.

107 **Measures**

108 At baseline, information on IC's age, gender, relationship with patient, marital status and
109 offspring were gathered. The CRA was collected at one-month follow-up after discharge. The
110 Caregiver Reaction Assessment scale (Spanish version) (CRA-SP) is a valid, reliable questionnaire
111 that evaluates the reactions of family caregivers of persons with mental impairments (Given et
112 al., 1992)(C. Alvira et al., 2020). Internal consistency had a Cronbach's alpha of 0.804. The
113 questionnaire is a 24-item Likert scale with response options ranging from strongly disagree to
114 strongly agree. A higher score on the caregiver self-esteem (7-35) subscale indicates a more
115 positive reaction to care, while a higher score in lack of family support (5-25), financial problems
116 (3-15), disrupted schedule (5-25) and health problems (4-20) shows more negative effects (Alvira
117 et al., 2020).

118 In addition, the Resource Utilization in Dementia (RUD) questionnaire was used to measure
119 resource utilization among older people with dementia and their caregivers, as well as the time
120 spent on formal and informal care by caregivers (Wimo et al., 2007). It is the most widely-used

121 tool for resource use in dementia and has been validated in several countries including Spain.
122 Data were collected regarding time dedicated by the IC to the PwD in activities of daily living
123 (bathing, dressing, toileting, transferring, continence and feeding) and instrumental activities of
124 daily living (cooking, medication, shopping, finance management, and transportation);
125 employment situation and lost IC productivity; and healthcare resources used (including
126 community and hospital services).

127 Furthermore, The Caregiver Experience Instrument is based on the Instrument to Evaluate the
128 Experience of Patients with Chronic Diseases (IEXPAC)(Guilabert et al., 2018). This recently
129 developed questionnaire in Spain explores elements of integrated health and social care for both
130 the patient and the caregiver, taking into account emotional, informational and personal
131 assistance from caregivers. The Caregiver Experience Instrument has adequate reliability,
132 internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha: 0.88), and construct and empirical validity. The scale was
133 developed in caregivers looking after people with generally chronic conditions including
134 neurological disorders. The questionnaire is a 12-item Likert scale with 4 additional items related
135 to situations that are common to this population group (hospitalization, emergency room, home
136 care and social services). Data were collected on admission, discharge, and at one-month and
137 three-month follow-up.

138

139 **Ethical considerations**

140 This study was approved by the Clinical Research Ethics Committee at each hospital; BLINDED.
141 Bearing in mind that participants presented dementia or cognitive impairment, they expressed
142 their willingness to participate accompanied by a family member, caregiver or legal guardian.
143 This study follows Declaration of Helsinki guidelines (World Medical Association, 2013).
144 Participants were able to withdraw from the study at any time. All data were treated in
145 accordance with EU Regulation 2016/679 of the European Parliament and Council of April 27th

146 2016 in relation to the handling of personal data, and Organic Law 3/2018 of 5th December on
147 Personal Data protection and digital rights warranty.

148

149 **Data analysis**

150 Descriptive data are presented as means and standard deviation (SD) for continuous variables
151 and numbers and percentages (%) for categorical variables. Estimated changes in IC outcomes
152 were studied with paired t-test for continuous variables and McNemar's test for categorical
153 variables. Outcomes assessed longitudinal changes from all the collection phases; baseline
154 (admission), discharge, one-month and three-month follow-up. Confidence intervals of 95%
155 were calculated. All significance tests were two-tailed and values of $p < 0.05$ were considered
156 significant. All analyses were conducted using the statistical software package R version 4.1.0.
157 for Windows.

158

159 **Rigor**

160 This study was conducted following the STROBE reporting standard for cohort studies (Von Elm
161 et al., 2008). Three hospitals were selected to amplify the sample size and increase its
162 representativeness of Spain.

163

164 **Results**

165 Baseline results show that ICs ($n=174$) were mostly women (71.8%) and the mean age was 62.6
166 ± 10.8 . Most ICs were the patients' offspring (71.3%), other family members (15.5%) or their
167 spouses (8%). Almost half of caregivers (42.5 %) lived with the patient and a third had children
168 (32.2%) (Table 1). Data on PwD has been published elsewhere (BLINDED et al., 2022).

169 Data on the IC reaction to caregiving were collected at one-month follow-up (n=141) post
170 discharge. Caregiver self-esteem was rated positively (28.1 ± 4.7); on the contrary the rest of
171 subscales were considered on the negative side; lack of family support (11.6 ± 3.7) and impact
172 on finances (7.9 ± 2.6), schedule (15.3 ± 4.3) and health (10.4 ± 3.5) (Table 2).

173 Data were also collected on caregiver work status and healthcare resource utilization on
174 admission and at 1-month follow-up post discharge. No statistical differences were noted
175 regarding IC time given to the patient. Number of hours per day dedicated to the patient
176 decreased slightly over time. IC spent 5.12 ± 7.03 hours per day assisting in activities of daily
177 living and 7.09 ± 8.16 on supervision at baseline. These hours fell, respectively, after 1 month;
178 4.75 ± 6.06 hours per day on activities of daily living and 6.21 ± 6.97 hours daily on supervision.

179 Regarding IC employment situation, only 21.3% had reached retirement age. On admission,
180 18.8% of caregivers were working less because of caregiving responsibilities, with a reduction of
181 13.5 ± 10.95 working hours per week. After one month, the number of working hours lost by ICs
182 dropped to 10.0 ± 8.38 hours per week.

183 Concerning IC resource utilization, 12.1% used inpatient care at baseline (9.2% visited the
184 emergency room and 4.3% were admitted to hospital at baseline), and 5% after 1 month (3.5%
185 used the emergency room and 2.1% were admitted to hospital). A total of 20.6% caregivers had
186 outpatient visits at baseline and 14.9% after 1 month. The main visits were to the family
187 physician. Some 18.4% of caregivers used community care at baseline and 12.8% after 1 month
188 (mainly district nurse). Statistical differences ($p=0.005$) were noted in district nurse
189 appointments, with 15.6% of caregivers receiving their care falling to 5% after one month (Table
190 3).

191 Caregiver Experiences in integrated health and social care were measured at baseline, discharge,
192 and at one and three-month follow-up. Differences were found when comparing overall scores
193 from admission 37.5 ± 11.57 and discharge 40.9 ± 10.06 ($p =0.028$), where hospitalization

194 seemed to improve the IC experience. After discharge, these scores were lower. Results are
195 presented in overall score and by item (Table 4).

196

197 Discussion

198

199 This study examined the reactions, experiences, resource utilization and work status of IC of
200 PwD or people with cognitive impairment and a proximal femur fracture requiring surgery during
201 and after hospitalization. This is the first study to analyze the profile of IC in relation to
202 hospitalization. ICs were mostly women, and numbers were slightly higher than the average
203 proportion of female caregivers according to OECD statistics (2019). Moreover, these were
204 mostly offspring and still at active working age. As shown in other studies, adult children of PwD
205 report higher burden than other family members. In addition, male IC continue being less active
206 with the caregiving role and are more likely to seek social support or formal caregivers than
207 female IC (Lee et al., 2021).

208 Our results indicate that reactions of IC during and after hospitalization are similar to those as
209 in homecare (Alvira et al., 2020). Minimal differences were noted in self-esteem, family support
210 and schedule dimensions, which were slightly more positive in our sample than in previous
211 studies (Alvira et al., 2020). Participants showed only positive attitudes in self-esteem. In
212 cultures where families tend to be close, caring for people in the family is culturally expected.
213 This elicits positive attitudes in regard to caring for older relatives and entails a higher level of
214 family involvement (Moreno-Cámara et al., 2019). Previous studies suggest that positive
215 attitudes could relate to feelings of meaningful and rewarding work (Alvira et al., 2015).
216 Caregivers that manifest more positive feelings from looking after their relatives show less
217 depression, better subjective health, lower burden and better emotional wellbeing. Conversely,

218 the other subscales (family support, impact on finances, schedule and health) showed negative
219 attitudes. Other studies report that ICs in Spain experience higher burden than ICs in other
220 European countries due to deficiencies in social healthcare resources. The main caregiver
221 assumes the role owing to the unavailability or unwillingness of another person to take on the
222 responsibilities and the lack of health services or home care (Sadavoy et al., 2022). Female IC
223 feel limited in accessing the labour market and, thus, improving their economic situation (Ruiz-
224 Adame Reina et al., 2017). Even after experiencing hospitalization, family members responsible
225 for their loved ones do not have respite from their care. Furthermore, almost 50% of participants
226 were actively employed. After hospitalization, ICs had less work absenteeism but continued to
227 dedicate considerable time to assistance, mostly on supervision of their relatives, followed by
228 activities of daily living such as bathing or feeding, and on instrumental activities including
229 shopping, cooking or transportation. However, ICs used fewer healthcare resources for
230 themselves after one-month follow-up. This was probably due to a higher burden of care and
231 not having the time to care for themselves.

232 Caregiver experiences on integrated health and social care were measured from admission to
233 three months after discharge. Overall caregiver experiences improved during hospitalization and
234 worsened slightly after three months. During hospitalization, care is provided by healthcare
235 staff, giving respite to ICs. After discharge, IC have to assume the caregiving role again, and this
236 might impact on their experiences. The items with the highest scores were with regard to
237 healthcare professionals ensuring the patient is taking the correct medication, which improved
238 during hospitalization. Nurses' awareness of medication safety is considered an indicator of
239 quality care provision. Another positively-valued item was related to professionals caring about
240 patients' well-being. Interestingly, results on caring about the caregiver's well-being were lower.
241 This demonstrates the importance of caring not only for the patient, but also for the caregiver
242 in the acute hospital setting. Furthermore, ICs had positive experiences with respect to knowing
243 where to contact services after discharge and how to achieve adequate home care. In contrast,

244 the items representing the worst experiences were related to healthcare professionals providing
245 information through the internet on websites and forums dealing with patients' illness issues. It
246 should be mentioned that some ICs may not be familiar with online resources. However, they
247 can be enthusiastic and efforts should be made to encourage portal use among caregivers
248 (Sarkar et al., 2015). Another item that should be improved relates to the lack of encouragement
249 to contact other caregivers or support groups. ICs could benefit from support groups and from
250 communication with other people in the same situation (Frias et al., 2020).

251 Hospitalization represents a good opportunity to approach IC and determine their needs to
252 provide them with interventions to minimize their burden and improve their wellbeing. These
253 interventions could deal with caregiving training, information about resources, engaging with
254 support groups or using relaxation techniques. Psychoeducational interventions for caregivers
255 on dementia are proven to be effective in minimizing burden, anxiety and depression (Frias et
256 al., 2020). Inclusion of ICs in care plans and decision-making improve their caregiving appraisal,
257 self-efficacy and well-being (Yoon & Kim, 2020) with respect to delivering patient-centered
258 care. Educating and empowering caregivers during hospitalization could also prepare a
259 smoother transition upon discharge.

260

261 **Limitations**

262 This study has some limitations. Each hospital included in the study belongs to a different
263 autonomous community, therefore variety of social and healthcare resources could be found,
264 and overall profile can vary among communities. However, as we included different areas in
265 Spain, we believe the sample is more heterogeneous and results can be more representative. As
266 the three participant university hospitals represent high technology centers with good standards
267 of care, these results could not be applicable to community or other hospitals. In addition,
268 completion of data collection from baseline to 3 months follow-up was challenging. Some of the

269 participants withdrew after discharge as the questionnaires were long and they did not wish to
270 continue due to burden. Also, we did not classify our results according to degree of dementia
271 severity, which could slightly alter the results. As severe dementia caregivers experience a higher
272 burden, results on experiences, reactions, resource utilization or employment situation could
273 differ.

274

275 Conclusion

276 IC have a heavy workload in caring for relatives with dementia hospitalized for a proximal femur
277 fracture. New policies should be considered to improve overall IC wellbeing and the PwD
278 experience of hospitalization to ensure smooth discharge and to provide the best possible
279 continuity of care to avoid institutionalization. Coordination among different healthcare levels
280 should also be improved to aid IC. Offering information, support and making IC feel involved in
281 the care process could be beneficial to ICs.

282 Conflict of interest

283 The authors declare there is no conflict of interest

284

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386

1 **Table 1**

2 *Sociodemographic characteristics of IC at baseline*

Variable	Total (n = 174)
	Mean ± SD
Age, years	62.6 ± 10.8
	n (%)
Gender, female	125 (71.8)
Relationship with PwD	
Spouse	14 (8.0)
Offspring	124 (71.3)
Other family members	27 (15.5)
Others	9 (5.2)
Marital status of IC	
Married/cohabitant	105 (60.3)
Never married	41 (23.6)
Divorced	22 (12.6)
Widowed	6 (3.5)
Caregiver has a child	56 (32.2)
Caregiver lives with PwD	74 (42.5)

3

4 **Table 2**

5 *Caregiver Reaction Assessment of IC one month after discharge*

CRA Subscale	Range	Mean (SD)
Caregiver self-esteem	11 - 35	28.1 ± 4.7
Lack of family support	5 - 24	11.6 ± 3.7
Impact on finances	3 - 15	7.9 ± 2.6
Impact on schedule	5 - 25	15.3 ± 4.3
Impact on health	4 - 19	10.4 ± 3.5

6

7

8 **Table 3**

9 *Comparison of caregiver work status and health care resource utilization between admission and*
 10 *1-month follow-up (n=141)*

Variable	Admission	One month follow-up	P value†
IC time			
Activities of daily living (days per month)	19.22 ± 12.05	20.52 ± 11.35	0.174
Activities of daily living (hours per day)	5.12 ± 7.03	4.75 ± 6.06	0.229
Instrumental activities of daily living (days per month)	20.68 ± 11.47	20.88 ± 11.26	0.902
Instrumental activities of daily living (hours per day)	4.42 ± 6.53	4.30 ± 6.15	0.687
Supervision (Hours per day)	7.09 ± 8.16	6.21 ± 6.97	0.093
Employment situation and lost productivity of IC			
Employment situation			0.288
Paid work	69 (48.9)	65 (46.1)	
Reached retirement age	29 (20.6)	30 (21.3)	
Early retirement (not disease-related)	13 (9.2)	11 (7.8)	
Worked less because of caregiving responsibilities	13 (18.8)	8 (12.3)	0.131
Hours per week reduced	13.5 ± 10.95	10.0 ± 8.38	0.316
Missed a full working day	1.54 ± 4.57	0.83 ± 3.79	0.031
Resource utilization of IC			
Emergency room (visit)	13 (9.2)	5 (3.5)	0.061
Outpatient care (visits)	29 (20.6)	21 (14.9)	0.256
Physician	28 (19.9)	20 (14.2)	0.243
Social worker	4 (2.8)	2 (1.4)	0.683
Psychologist	5 (3.5)	3 (2.1)	0.617
Nurse	9 (6.4)	8 (5.7)	1.000
Community care	26 (18.4)	18 (12.8)	0.243
District nurse (visit)	22 (15.6)	7 (5)	0.005

11 Data are presented as number (percentage) or means ± standard deviation.

12 † Paired t-test or McNemar's test

13 In bold, statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) differences between admission and 1-month follow-up

14

15

16 **Table 4**

17 *Caregiver experiences of IC on admission, discharge, one-month follow-up and three months*

18 *follow-up*

Variable	Admission	Discharge	One-month follow-up	Three-month follow-up	<i>P value</i>[†]	<i>P value</i>[‡]	<i>P value</i>[§]
Total	37.5 ± 11.57	40.9 ± 10.06	38.76 ± 9.33	38.19 ± 7.88	0.028	0.004	0.439

19

† Comparison between admission and 1-month follow-up (paired t-test or McNemar's test)

‡ Comparison between admission and 3-month follow-up (paired t-test or McNemar's test)

§ Comparison between 1-month follow-up and 3-month follow-up (paired t-test or McNemar's test)

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